
Review

Discussion on the Planning of Infrastructure from the Perspective of Smart City

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Abstract: Smart cities are the use of modern information technology and innovative technology to view a city as an organic entity, effectively integrating and linking various functional areas of traditional cities. By optimizing urban management and services, it improves the operational efficiency of the city and enhances the quality of life for its citizens. Therefore, starting from practice, we will analyze the planning and construction of communication infrastructure from the perspective of smart city development, explore its construction principles and planning directions, and provide some thoughts for the construction of smart cities.

Keywords: Smart city; Development; Communication infrastructure; Planning and Construction

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1. Introduction

1.1 Overview of Smart City Construction

Smart cities consist of eight key elements, covering multiple aspects such as urban design, construction, operation, management, and security, including top-level design, institutional mechanisms, infrastructure, urban operation center, smart governance, smart ecology, standard system for technological innovation, and security guarantees.

The construction of smart cities in China has gone through three stages. The first stage is the initial stage of smart city construction, from 2008 to 2012. The characteristic of this stage is that the concept of smart cities has just emerged, and various fields are promoting the digital and intelligent transformation of industries separately, but the construction lacks overall coordination. The second stage is the rapid development period of smart city construction, from 2012 to 2015. During this period, smart cities were in a stage of continuous exploration and development. Under the guidance of relevant national departments, various business application fields began to explore layout, linkage, and sharing. The third stage is from 2016 to present, which is the gradual maturity stage of smart cities. The development concept, construction ideas, implementation path, operation mode, technological means and other aspects of smart cities are upgraded and iterated in all aspects, entering the mature stage of people-oriented, coordinated, and intensive, collaborative innovation, and heavy planning and layout.

1.2 Basic Principles of Smart City Construction

Firstly, the principle of reasonableness. The construction of smart cities must adhere to the principle of rationality, (1) comply with national policies and regulations, (2) comply with industry standards, and (3) comply with technical specifications to ensure that the construction results can meet the established goals and achieve the expected functions and effects.

Secondly, the principle of scientific. The construction of smart cities requires scientific research. The layout, top-level planning, design, implementation, and other aspects of smart city construction require scientific planning, design, management, and maintenance. Smart city construction is not simply about replicating experience, but rather about planning according to local conditions based on seeking truth from facts, to ensure that there are no major risks or loopholes in actual operation and to ensure the smooth progress of the plan.

Figure 1 Overview of Smart city

2. The necessity of constructing communication infrastructure

As the construction of smart cities enters a mature stage, the connotation and extension of smart city development are constantly improving, forming a systematic theory. This does not mean that smart city construction has become standardized and simplified. On the contrary, in the current stage of accumulating rich experience, the complexity of smart city construction is increasing day by day, and the requirements for scientific and coordinated top-level design are higher. Top level design should be planned with a far sighted perspective, highlighting the effect of integrating the entire domain; Secondly, graded promotion emphasizes differentiated layout; Finally, functional differentiation and integration promote coordinated operation.

The construction of communication infrastructure is the foundation of smart cities. If a smart city is a high-rise building, the communication infrastructure is the foundation of the building. Only infrastructure with reasonable planning, standardized design, and forward-looking can effectively support the requirements of network capability and network quality for smart city construction. Exploring strategic facilities that integrate perception, transmission, storage, computing, and processing is a necessary condition for supporting urban economic and social development. With the diminishing marginal benefits of traditional "iron public infrastructure" construction, as well as the rise of new generation communication networks and urban functional upgrades, the demand for communication infrastructure has undergone significant changes, and the demand for compatibility between communication infrastructure and smart cities will rapidly expand.

3.1 Content of planning and construction of communication infrastructure for smart cities

Under the framework of smart cities, this article will explore the direction and layout of communication infrastructure construction, and analyze from the aspects of mobile networks, broadband networks, data centers, etc.

Figure 2 Content of planning and construction of communication infrastructure for smart cities

3.1 Mobile Network Construction

The current basic network of smart cities is based on 4G networks, which can be said to witness the growth and development of smart cities. The urban coverage rate of 4G network in China has exceeded 98%, and more than half of the cities have achieved continuous coverage of 4G network. The 4G network coverage rate of administrative villages will also reach over 98% by the end of the 13th Five Year Plan period. The wide coverage and high-quality 4G mobile network support most mobile applications in smart cities, with high user perception.

With the commercialization of 5G, new momentum has been injected into the construction of smart cities. At present, several major cities including Beijing, Shanghai, Guangzhou, Shenzhen, Chongqing, and Hangzhou have planned to complete the construction of more than 10000 5G base stations by the end of 2019. Multiple provinces and cities across the country have introduced supporting policies to encourage operators to accelerate the construction of 5G networks and achieve commercial use of 5G networks as soon as possible. On June 6, 2019, China Mobile, China Unicom, China Telecom, and China Radio and Television obtained 5G commercial licenses issued by the Ministry of Industry and Information Technology, and 5G construction was quickly put on the agenda.

The scale construction and commercial potential of 5G mobile networks empower the construction of smart cities. Urban construction, with the construction of 5G networks as the starting point, can cultivate the 5G industry system, promote the integration of 5G construction and vertical industry applications, and penetrate almost all fields of smart city construction, providing real-time response and efficient linkage 5G application solutions for municipal infrastructure, power grid, water affairs, transportation, medical care, and even ocean management. The low latency and high bandwidth characteristics of 5G are currently the mainstream applications. In more than 40 pilot cities across the country, 5G+high-definition live streaming application projects have a coverage rate of over 70% in pilot cities. 5G+autonomous driving, connected vehicles, remote surgery and other applications that require high real-time performance are also among the top. From this, the construction of 5G networks will provide fanatical support for the development of smart cities towards a smarter direction. Scientific layout and planning of 5G networks, promoting the large-scale construction of 5G networks, and exploring their wide application scenarios are essential to the construction of new smart cities.

3.2 Broadband Network Construction

In the construction of smart cities, in order to achieve full coverage of broadband networks, effectively improve the speed of broadband traffic, and meet the requirements of urban residents for broadband, DWDM all-optical equipment can be selected as the transmission network for data information to ensure that broadband has a large capacity and

strong reliability. Improving broadband bandwidth and achieving full coverage of urban and rural broadband networks is the foundation for realizing intelligent applications in smart cities.

3.3 Data Center Construction

In the planning and construction process of smart city communication infrastructure, attention should be paid to the construction of data centers, and efforts should be made to create a cloud computing environment with large storage capacity, high security performance, strong information processing capabilities, and the ability to use different services. In 2019, the Ministry of Industry and Information Technology issued the "Guiding Opinions on Strengthening the Construction of Green Data Centers", which clearly stated that the design energy efficiency value of large and ultra large data centers should not exceed 1.4, and the energy efficiency value of renovating existing large and ultra large data centers should not exceed 1.8. Promoting the construction of high-power and low-energy data centers that meet the requirements of efficient, environmentally friendly, fast, and convenient smart cities is an important part of the construction of communication infrastructure in smart cities.

3.4 Construction of Smart Housing Services

Smart housing services play a significant role in the overall planning and construction of communication infrastructure, directly reflecting the original intention and purpose of smart city construction. Therefore, before carrying out smart housing services, it is necessary to conduct research and pilot projects in residential areas. After carefully observing and analyzing the service results, it is necessary to scientifically and plan smart housing services based on the actual characteristics and needs of different regions, to ensure various needs in public areas, residential and business areas, etc. In addition, services can be provided based on the characteristics of the region. For example, in business areas, a smart office system can be created to improve the work efficiency of staff; In residential areas, community monitoring systems can be established to improve the safety level of the community.

4. New exploration of communication infrastructure in smart cities

In the construction of communication infrastructure in smart cities, the construction of mobile networks, broadband networks, and data centers should be demand-oriented, guided by planning blueprints and goals, designing network capacity, and designing storage space for data centers. Based on balancing demand and cost, scientifically plan, and construct the layout to maximize the efficiency of the network and data center.

The location selection of communication base stations has always been a difficult and painful point in the construction of communication networks. The traditional approach is to set up as many small, distributed base stations as possible to expand the coverage area of wireless networks. In recent years, the emergence of smart streetlights or smart poles has solved the problem of site selection for base stations. Smart poles can integrate communication infrastructure and municipal infrastructure. By integrating multiple functions such as smart lighting, WIFI, pseudo base stations, urban monitoring, and electric piles, they break through the boundaries of traditional poles and integrate functional modules such as smart gateways and edge computing to achieve data integration and smart management. Smart poles have become a key component of new smart city intelligent facilities, and governments at all levels are actively promoting the construction of smart poles. In May 2018, the Ministry of Industry and Information Technology and the State owned Assets Supervision and Administration Commission jointly issued the "Implementation Opinions on Promoting the Co construction and Sharing of Telecommunications Infrastructure in 2018", which pointed out that efforts should be made to actively promote the two-way sharing of communication towers, street lights, monitoring, traffic signs and other light pole resources, and to promote the "integration of multiple towers" and "integration of multiple poles". The construction of smart poles has been rapidly promoted.

5. Conclusion

Smart cities are an advanced stage of modern urban construction, which is a product of higher human requirements for living and living environments. The construction of smart cities is not a scattered patchwork of information technology, nor a simple superposition of urban functions. Smart cities are built on a solid foundation of new generation

communication infrastructure, through scientific top-level design, planning, and layout, constantly researching and applying new technological means to solve construction difficulties and pain points, and overall planning and construction. They are the crystallization of the wisdom of communication infrastructure and urban construction.

References

- [1] Wiig, “(e empty rhetoric of the smart city: from digitalinclusion to economic promotion in Philadelphia,” *UrbanGeography*, vol. 37, no. 4, pp. 535–553, 2016.
- [2] Gaffney and C. Robertson, “Smarter than smart: rio deJaneiro’s flawed emergence as a smart city,” *Journal of UrbanTechnology*, vol. 25, no. 3, pp. 47–64, 2018
- [3] F. Li, A. Nucciarelli, S. Roden, and G. Graham, “How smartcities transform operations models: a new research agenda foroperations management in the digital economy,” *ProductionPlanning & Control*, vol. 27, no. 6, pp. 514–528, 2016.
- [4] G. V. Pereira, M. A. Macadar, E. M. Luciano, and M. G. Testa, “Delivering public value through open government datainitiatives in a smart city context,” *Information SystemsFrontiers*, vol. 19, no. 2, pp. 213–229, 2017.
- [5] H. Yeh, “(e effects of successful ICT-based smart city ser-vices: from citizens’ perspectives,” *Government Infor-mationQuarterly*, vol. 34, no. 3, pp. 556–565, 2017.
- [6] J. Wang, C. Jiang, K. Zhang et al., “Vehicular sensing networksin a smart city: principles, technologies and appli-cations,”*IEEE Wireless Communications*, vol. 25, no. 1, pp. 122–132,2017.
- [7] K. Vu and K. Hartley, “Promoting smart cities in developingcountries: policy insights from Vietnam,” *Telecom-munica-tions Policy*, vol. 42, no. 10, pp. 845–859, 2018.
- [8] M. Kriv’y, “Towards a critique of cybernetic urbanism: thesmart city and the society of control,” *Planning ;eory*, vol. 17,no. 1, pp. 8–30, 2018.
- [9] H. Gandy and S. Nemorin, “Toward a political economy ofnudge: smart city variations,” *Information, Communi-cation &Society*, vol. 22, no. 14, pp. 2112–2126, 2019.
- [10] V. Niaros, V. Kostakis, and W. Drechsler, “Making (in) thesmart city: the emergence of makerspaces,” *Telematics andInformatics*, vol. 34, no. 7, pp. 1143–1152, 2017.
- [11] Y. Hayashi, Y. Fujimoto, H. Ishii et al., “Versatile modelingplatform for cooperative energy management systems insmart cities,” *Proceedings of the IEEE*, vol. 106, no. 4,pp. 594–612, 2018.

